

Paleogene Paleoenvironments of the Doldenhorn Nappe: from short-lived carbonate shoals to hemipelagic slope (Lämmerenalp, VS)

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The Paleogene of the Doldenhorn Nappe in the Gemmi-Lämmerenalp area has not been assigned to lithostratigraphic formations and lacks precise biochronology and paleoenvironmental interpretation. Furrer (1962) briefly described the Eocene formations of the area and mentioned *Nummulites incrassatus* De La Harpe, typical of the Late Eocene, among other fossils from the NW-slopes of the Doldenhorn. Herb in Masson et al. (1980) gave an excellent description of the Jurassic to Eocene section of the Doldenhorn nappe in the area. Gansner (2000) described the Eocene sections of the Lämmerenalp. Here, we assign the Paleogene sediments in stratigraphic order to: the Siderolithic, the Santesch and the Stad Formations.

The **Siderolithic** Formation is characterized by terrestrial Fe-hydroxide crusts and red shales with pisolites, occurring in paleo-karst pockets in the underlying Lower Cretaceous formations (Schrattenkalk and Thierwis), which are often pervasively invested by *Microcodium*.

The Priabonian **Sanetsch** Formation (Menkveld-Gfeller, 1994) onlaps unconformably on a paleorelief with several facies: The lowest (and in places oldest) facies consist of dark grey shaly limestones rich in fossils, including solitary and hermatypic corals, oysters and other bivalves, sponges, and in some places *Cerithium* sp. This facies (“*Cerithium* beds”) can be assigned to the **Diablerets Member** of the Sanetsch Formation. It represents a paralic to brackish paleo-environment containing terrestrial and coastal organic matter. This facies occurs with up to 10 m thickness at Rote Chumme (Herb in Masson et al. 1980) and interfingers with lithothamnid limestones S of the Lämmerensee. At Lämmerenplatten normal marine facies assignable to the **Tsanfleuron Member** of the Sanetsch Formation onlap on the Lower Cretaceous substrate with marine conglomerates containing bored limestone clasts in a sandy matrix, and coral colonies in former karst depressions. Well washed, carbonate poor, parallel and cross-bedded quartz sandstone sheets alternate with massive, sometimes sandy limestones composed of both geniculate and melobesian red algae, corals, bivalves and echinids (*Clypeaster* sp). Rare, small nummulites such as *Nummulites retiatus* Roveda (Fig. 1a) indicate a Priabonian age, already mentioned by Herb (1988) in the Priabonian of the Doldenhorn nappe of the Kiental. Some levels may correspond to algal boundstones, others represent micrite-rich packstones with miliolids, representing lagoonal facies. Sharp bases of the sandstone sheets suggest sudden demise of the short-lived carbonate shoals and onset of quartz sand-dominated sealevel lowstand sedimentation. The topmost, massive, 6-8 m thick limestone bed is richer in *Nummulites* spp. and contains less quartz sand. Well preserved colonies of the coral *Cladocora* sp. (Fig. 1b) attest for a blue water

shallow carbonate environment, assignable to the **Pierredar Limestone Member** of the Sanetsch Formation.

To the NE of the Lämmerensee, along a vertical cliff (Fig. 1c), the topmost Pierredar Limestone bed folds into a narrow, overturned limb and is stratigraphically overlain by a light yellowish-grey shaly hemipelagic limestone with globigerinids, assignable to the **Stad Formation**. The sharp change from shallow carbonate to pelagic facies is interpreted as tectonic drowning in front of the Alpine orogen, close to the Eocene/Oligocene boundary.

Figure 1. a.- b Outcrop images of the Pierredar Limestone fossils, Lämmerenalp (VS). a. *Nummulites retiatus* axial sections in quartzose (dark grey) limestone. b. *Cladocora* sp. shallow water coral colony, topmost Pierredar Limestone. c. Top of Pierredar Lst. and overturned stratigraphic contact with hemipelagic Stad Formation, NE of Lämmerensee (middle right).

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